

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF AFFIXES IN THE FORMATION OF MILITARY-TECHNICAL TERMS IN CHINESE AND UZBEK LANGUAGE

Salimova Sokhiba Bazarboyevna

Doctoral Student of Termiz State University, Uzbekistan

Makhfirat Kurbonaliyeva

Associate Professor of Termez State University, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19888083>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24th April 2026

Accepted: 26th April 2026

Online: 28th April 2026

KEYWORDS

Linguistic, semantic, contextual factors, types of affixes, comparative research process

ABSTRACT

This article provides information about affixes that helps to understand the translation process more deeply, helps in creating manuals, and shows that each lexicon has its own approach and significance.

Introduction

The issue of word formation in the Uzbek language dates back to a long history in linguistics. Fundamental issues of word formation are acknowledged in the works of Qoshg'ariy, Navoiy, Beruniy, Zamahshariy, and M. Chingizi. The consensus reached by Chinese scholars on the topic of affixation had already been established by Uzbek linguists in their earlier research. Ayyub G'ulomov's contribution to the issue of affixation in the Uzbek language is unparalleled. "It is known that studying historical word formation plays a significant role in creating the historical grammar of the language. This independent linguistic subject is also of great importance for historical lexicology." From this perspective, we focused our scientific work on the issue of affixation and its evolution. We consider understanding the basic principles to be the most effective aid in the analysis of technical terms. A. G'ulomov was the first to scientifically research the issue of word formation in Uzbek linguistics, analyzing word formation as a separate section, similar to phonetics, morphology, and other fields. In Uzbek linguistics, the formation of the section on word formation can be compared to the works of Professor G'ulomov with the 马氏文通 (Ma Shi Wen Tong) in the Chinese scientific community regarding the system of terms related to this section. In this regard, not only Uzbek but also Russian scholars have analyzed the issue of word formation and produced works. The creation of the fundamental work "Grammar of Modern Uzbek Literary Language" by Kissen serves as an example. According to G.I. Ramstedt's perspective on word formation, the morphology of languages is crucial in their word formation processes. Considering that there are significant differences in the evolutionary processes of the Chinese and Uzbek languages, we also address their types. Linguists typically categorize languages into several groups based on their morphological characteristics: agglutinative, inflectional, isolating, and polysynthetic languages. Each type of language has its own unique characteristics in word formation and inflection. In agglutinative languages, affixes serve a single function, follow

simple rules, and have specific attachments. In inflectional languages, affixes have various functions and complex changes, and the combination of roots and affixes is flexible. Isolating languages have little inflection and rely on word order and function words to express grammatical relationships. Polysynthetic languages feature complex forms of words, where a single word expresses complex sentence structures and grammatical relationships. These classifications are abstractions and simplifications of linguistic morphological characteristics. In reality, there may be a mix types in languages. For example, while the Chinese language is primarily an isolating language, it also exhibits some characteristics of agglutinative languages.

The research work "Formation of Verbs in the Uzbek Language" (2009) by U. Tursunov, along with A. G'ulomov's works on the "-ka affix" (1946), "About the -la affix in the Uzbek language" (1947), "Methods of Word Formation in the Uzbek Language" (1949), and "Some Issues of Affixation in the Uzbek Language" (1953), as well as S.A. Akbarov's candidate dissertation "Compound Verbs in the Uzbek Language" (1950), Z. Ma'rufov's analysis of "Affixes that Form Nouns" (1940), and Y. Tojiyev's research on "Affix Synonymy," have all significantly contributed to the establishment of the principles of word formation in the Uzbek language.

The importance of G'ulomov's work lies in the fact that he examined word formation issues comparatively, referencing the scientific works of many scholars, including M.I. Odilov on word formation in the Azerbaijani language and P. Azimov on word formation in the Turkmen language. The foundations of word formation in Ayyub G'ulomov's linguistic views are reflected in his works such as "Determinatives in the Uzbek Language" (1940), "Cases in the Uzbek Language" (1941), "The Category of Plurality in the Uzbek Language" (1944), "Stress in the Uzbek Language" (1947), "Simple Sentence Syntax" (1948), "Methods of Word Formation in the Uzbek Language" (1949), "Verb" (1954), "Simple Sentence" (1955), "Modern Uzbek Literary Language. Syntax" (Hamkor, 1965, 2nd edition), "Grammar of the Uzbek Language" (Vol. I. Morphology, Hamkor, 1975), and "Morpheme Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" (Hamkor, 1973).

In the word formation system of the Uzbek language, the methods of affixation (morphological) and composition (syntactic) are primarily active, where an additional morpheme is attached to the base morpheme. "In the affixation method of word formation, the creation of a new word-morpheme is understood as adding an affix or a word-modifying element to the base word."

From the perspective of linguistic typology, the Chinese language stands out for its limited morphological variability. Word formation is primarily based on compounding. Affixes and root words constitute a small part of the overall vocabulary. However, affixes are the smallest and most debated grammatical units in the Chinese language, with existing disagreements regarding their terminology, criteria, and scope of use.

"In order to analyze modern Chinese affixes, research methods, corpus sources, and fundamental theoretical issues regarding affixes in modern Chinese must be logically and terminologically compared. This includes the classification of lexical affixes (word-modifying, such as prefixes, suffixes, infixes) and morphological affixes (word-forming, such as prefixes and additions), which requires a scientific approach."

Conclusion

The existence of affixes serves as an important tool for the formation and evolution of the Chinese lexicon. Chinese affixes possess a strong ability to create new words by combining with various word roots, capable of generating numerous new terms. These new words often inherit the core meaning of the root word while simultaneously producing new meanings and usages through the semantic function of the affix. This method of word formation has allowed for a rapid quantitative growth of the Chinese vocabulary, while also enriching the lexicon in terms of meaning and nuance.

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